

Extraction Chromatographic Studies of Mercury(II) with SRS-100

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Mercury(II) has been extracted at pH 4.5–6.0 from ammonium acetate-acetic acid buffer on silica gel column impregnated with SRS-100 (a high molecular mass carboxylic acid). The extracted mercury(II) after elution with 0.1 M HNO₃ has been estimated complexometrically. The effects of pH, stripping agents, flow rate on extraction and elution have been studied. Exchange capacity and breakthrough capacity of the exchanger with respect to mercury(II) have been determined. The exchanger has been successfully used for quantitative separation of mercury(II) from a number of ions in synthetic mixture.

Extraction and determination of small amount mercury from toxic industrial effluents have attracted considerable attention^{1,2}. Amberlite LA-1 and capric acid have been used in our laboratory for the extraction, separation and determination of mercury³. As liquid cation exchanger, versatic acid (high molecular mass water-insoluble carboxylic acid) have been used². However, extraction chromatographic behaviour of mercury(II) with SRS-100 (a liquid cation exchanger) has not been reported in the literature. This paper reports the systematic study on extraction chromatographic behaviour of mercury(II) on silica gel column impregnated with SRS-100.

Results and Discussion

Extraction in the pH range 3.5–6.0 from acetate buffer showed that mercury(II) was quantitatively extracted at pH 5.0–6.0. Flow rates upto 2 ml min⁻¹ during extraction showed complete retention of mercury(II) in the column. Common anions like NO₃⁻ and SO₄²⁻ did not interfere.

Sulphuric acid, nitric acid, acetic acid, ammonium nitrate and deionised water were used as the stripping agents. Complete stripping of mercury(II) was achieved with 0.1 M nitric acid, 0.2 M sulphuric acid and 0.5 M acetic acid. A 0.1 M nitric acid gave best result. Therefore in all experiments 0.1 M nitric acid was preferred as stripping agent.

Separation of Hg^{II} from binary mixtures : It was possible to separate mercury(II) from several elements in binary mixtures. At pH 5.0, metal ions like Mg^{II}, Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III} and U^{VI} passed through the column with the mobile phase but mercury(II) was extracted. After extraction, mercury(II) was eluted with 0.1 M nitric acid. Binary mixture containing mercury(II) with Fe^{III} or Zr^{IV} was passed through the column at pH 2.6, where mercury(II) passed through the column, the other metal ions were extracted. Fe^{III} was eluted with 0.1 M HCl and Zr^{IV} with 8 M HNO₃. The separation of mercury(II) from Cu^{II}, Cd^{II}, Ce^{IV}, Pb^{II}, Bi^{III} and Th^{IV} was achieved by passing the binary mixture through the column at pH 5 (in case of Cd^{II}, pH was 5.8) when each of the foreign ions along with mercury(II) were extracted. In all these cases ex-

cepting Cd^{II} and Cu^{II}, mercury(II) was selectively eluted first with 0.1 M HNO₃ followed by stripping of the diverse ions. Cd^{II} was eluted with 0.001 M HNO₃, Cu^{II} with 0.02 M HNO₃, Pb^{II}, Bi^{III} with 1 M HNO₃, Ce^{IV} with 1 M H₂SO₄, Th^{IV} with 1 : 1 (v/v) 0.2 M HNO₃ and 0.2 M NaNO₃ solution. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SEPARATION OF Hg^{II} FROM BINARY MIXTURES*

Metal ion	Wt. of metal ion (mg)		Recovery of Hg (mg)	Eluent used
	Added	Recovered		
Mg ^{II}	4.40	4.40	3.40	—
Cr ^{III}	1.30	1.31	3.40	—
Mn ^{II}	2.00	2.00	3.40	—
Fe ^{IIIa}	3.00	2.98	3.42	0.1 M HCl
Co ^{II}	2.04	2.02	3.42	—
Ni ^{II}	4.50	4.50	3.40	—
Cu ^{II}	1.39	1.40	3.39	0.02 M HNO ₃
Zn ^{II}	3.79	3.79	3.40	—
Zr ^{IVa}	3.09	3.06	3.43	8 M HNO ₃
Cd ^{IIb}	2.44	2.43	3.41	0.001 M HNO ₃
La ^{III}	3.60	3.60	3.40	—
Ce ^{IV}	3.36	3.36	3.40	1 M H ₂ SO ₄
Nd ^{III}	3.20	3.16	3.44	—
Sm ^{IV}	2.10	2.08	3.42	—
Gd ^{III}	5.03	5.00	3.40	—
Tl ^{III}	3.27	3.26	3.41	0.01 M HCl
Pb ^{II}	2.60	2.57	3.43	1 M HNO ₃
Bi ^{III}	2.00	1.98	3.42	0.8 M HNO ₃
Th ^{IV}	3.20	3.10	3.50	1 : 1 (v/v) 0.2 M HNO ₃ and 2 M NaNO ₃
U ^{VI}	4.28	4.28	3.40	—

*Average of five determinations. ^apH = 2.6, ^bpH = 5.8.

Separation of Hg^{II} from synthetic multicomponent mixtures : In order to assess the possible analytical application, the proposed method was applied to separate mercury(II) from several synthetic mixtures containing Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Zr^{IV}, Cd^{II}, Ce^{IV}, Tl^{III}, Pb^{II}, Th^{IV} etc. along with mercury(II). The results are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—SEPARATION OF Hg^{II} FROM SYNTHETIC MIXTURES*

Hg^{II} Taken = 3.41 mg, column = 1 × 8.5 cm, flow rate = 1 ml min⁻¹,
pH = 5.0

Sl. no.	Cations	Wt. of metal ion (mg)		Recovery %	Eluent used	Eluent vol. (ml)
		Added	Recovered			
1. ^a	Zn ^{II}	3.8	3.8	100	—	40
	Cd ^{II}	2.4	2.34	98	0.001 M HNO ₃	40
	Hg ^{II}	3.41	3.42	100.2	0.1 M HNO ₃	40
2.	Zn ^{II}	3.80	3.8	100	—	40
	Cu ^{II}	1.39	1.40	101.4	0.02 M HNO ₃	30
	Hg ^{II}	3.41	3.40	98	0.1 M HNO ₃	40
3. ^a	Cd ^{II}	2.40	2.34	98	0.001 M HNO ₃	40
	Cu ^{II}	1.34	1.40	101.4	0.02 M HNO ₃	30
	Hg ^{II}	3.41	3.42	100.1	0.1 M HNO ₃	40
4.	Cr ^{III}	1.30	1.28	98.5	—	30
	Hg ^{II}	3.41	3.40	99.7	0.1 M HNO ₃	40
	Pb ^{II}	2.60	2.62	100.7	1 M HNO ₃	40
5.	Tl ^{III}	3.27	3.26	99	0.01 M HCl	40
	Hg ^{II}	3.41	3.42	100.2	0.1 M HNO ₃	40
	Pb ^{II}	2.60	2.61	100.4	1 M HNO ₃	40
6. ^b	Fe ^{III}	3.00	2.98	99	0.1 M HCl	30
	Hg ^{II}	3.41	3.40	99.7	0.1 M HNO ₃	40
	Pb ^{II}	2.60	2.63	100.1	1 M HNO ₃	40
7.	Zn ^{II}	3.80	3.80	100	—	40
	Tl ^{IV}	3.27	3.26	99.6	0.1 M HNO ₃	40
	Hg ^{II}	3.41	3.41	100	0.1 M HNO ₃	40
	Bi ^{III}	4.10	4.10	100	0.8 M HNO ₃	20

*Average of five determinations. ^apH = 5.8. ^bpH = 2.6.

Experimental

An ECIL 5652A pH meter provided with a combined glass electrode, a hot-cum-cold bath (Dimmerstat 7D-1E) and chromatographic column (1.0 × 8.5 cm) of borosil glass was used. The liquid cation exchanger, SRS-100 (Shell Chemical, London), a high molecular synthetic monocarboxylic acid (C₁₅-C₁₆), was used without any further purification. A stock solution of Hg^{II} (3.4 mg ml⁻¹) was standardised complexometrically with EDTA⁴. Buffer solutions of different pH were prepared with 0.2 M acetic acid and 0.2 M ammonium acetate. All chemicals and solvents were of A.R. grade unless otherwise stated.

Preparation of ion-exchange material : Silica gel (30–120 mesh, B.D.H.) was rendered hydrophobic by exposing

it to the vapour of dimethyl dichlorosilane in nitrogen atmosphere. The hydrophobic silica gel was washed with methanol and dried at 100°. The dried gel was impregnated with SRS-100 diluted in benzene and dried to produce a uniform coating. Excess benzene was washed with HCl (2 M). In routine work, 1 ml dimethyldichlorosilane is adequate for 10 g silica gel, and 1 g of hydrophobic gel can take up about 0.7 ml of SRS-100. For column work, the coated silica gel (2.5 g) was slurried with 20 ml of distilled water (20 ml) and poured into the column. Each column was found usable for at least 25 cycles without loss of extraction capacity.

The exchange capacity of the exchanger was found to be 1.65 meq of H⁺/g at 25°. The breakthrough capacity of the exchanger with respect to Hg^{II} was determined at pH 5 and 6 as per literature method. It was observed that SRS-100 impregnated silica gel (1 g) can load 38 and 60 mg of Hg^{II} quantitatively at pH 5 and pH 6 respectively.

Extraction procedure : An aqueous solution containing 3.41 mg/ml⁻¹ Hg^{II} was mixed with the buffer solution and its pH was adjusted to 5.6. The solution was passed through silica gel column coated with SRS-100 at a flow rate of 1 ml min⁻¹. pH of the exchanger bed was adjusted to 5.6 before passing the metal ion solution in each operation. After extraction mercury(II) was eluted with mineral acid and its amount in each fraction was determined complexometrically.

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